

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EARLY DETECTION AND MOLECULAR DIAGNOSIS OF CERVICAL CANCER USING STEM CELL MARKERS (CK19, NESTIN, AND CD133)

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ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer is one of the leading causes of cancer death among females worldwide and its behavior epidemiologically likes a venereal disease of low infectiousness. Early age at first intercourse and multiple sexual partners have been shown to exert strong effects on risk. The wide differences in the incidence among different countries also influenced by the introduction of screening. Although the general picture remains one of decreasing incidence and mortality, there are signs of an increasing cervical cancer risk probably due to changes in sexual behavior. Smoking and human papillomavirus (HPV) 16/18 are currently important issues in a concept of multifactorial, stepwise carcinogenesis at the cervix uteri. Therefore, society-based preventive and control measures, screening activities and HPV vaccination are recommended. Cervical cancer screening methods have evolved from cell morphology observation to molecular testing. High-risk HPV

genotyping and liquid-based cytology are common methods which have been widely recommended and used worldwide. In future, accurate, cheap, fast and easy-to-use methods would be more popular. Artificial intelligence also shows to be promising in cervical cancer screening by integrating image recognition with big data technology. Meanwhile, China has achieved numerous breakthroughs in cervical cancer prevention and control which could be a great demonstration for other developing and resource-limited areas. In conclusion, although

cervical cancer threatens female health, it could be the first cancer that would be eliminated by human beings with comprehensive preventive and control strategy.

KEYWORDS: Cervical cancer, epidemiology, risk factors, screening.

INTRODUCTION

A model that explains the phenotypic and functional heterogeneity of cancer cells within the same tumor is the cancer stem cell (CSC) model. According to the CSC model, a tumor has a hierarchical cellular structure, where a small population of tumorigenic CSCs differentiates into non-stem cancer cells or non-tumorigenic progeny.^[1] Cancer stem cells are thought to possess stem-like properties of self-renewal, and initiate and drive tumor growth and metastasis, in addition to therapy resistance and recurrence following conventional therapy.^[2] As genital infection with human papillomaviruses (HPVs), in particular the persistent infection of high-risk species (including HPV16 and 18), promotes disease progression from cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) to malignancy, the virus may interact with CSCs in the epithelium of the uterine cervix.^[3,4]

In general, the cervix is composed of hard squamous cells in the ectocervix, soft columnar cells in the endocervix and metaplastic cells in the squamocolumnar junction, also known as the transformation zone.^[5] Squamous and columnar epithelial cells are regenerated by the active division of stem-like reserve cells in the transformation zone, where cervical cancer is hypothesized to originate.^[6,7] It has been suggested that HPV enters the cell by distinct pathways, including clathrin- or caveolar-mediated endocytosis, or alternative routes in which tetraspanin-enriched microdomains are involved.^[8] The dependence of HPV infection on the activity of cyclin dependent kinases and microtubule reorganization, suggests that the incorporation of the viral genome into the nucleus of reserve cells may require the cell to enter into mitosis.^[9] HPV may program the cell to undergo symmetric division, by the disturbance of asymmetric division, therefore allowing the cells to proliferate and produce viral particles, but preventing them from differentiation.^[10,11] Accordingly, reserve cells may be converted to cervical CSCs by the interplay with high risk-HPV viral oncogenes and cellular alterations during cervical carcinogenesis.^[11] In fact, the presence of CSCs in cervical carcinoma is detectable by using stem cell markers. Early studies suggested that transcription factor tumor protein p63 (p63) and cytokeratin 17 (KRT17) are markers for reserve cells and reserve cell hyperplasia in the epithelium of cervical lesions and are upregulated during HPV infection of epithelial cells.^[10,12,13] Nanog homeobox (NANOG), POU class 5 homeobox 1

(OCT4) and SRY-box 2 (SOX2) are key regulators of embryonic stem cells and incorporate primarily into the regulatory network responsible for self-renewal and pluripotency.^[14,15] NANOG is expressed in cervical lesions but may not associate with the prognosis of cervical carcinoma.^[16] Different isoforms of OCT4 are expressed in cultured cells of cervical carcinoma, with the highest level in HPV-positive cells.^[17,18] Aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH), a stem cell marker for early stem-cell differentiation, is detectable in cervical epithelial lesions and carcinoma in addition to stem-like cells that are isolated from cervical carcinoma cells.^[19-21] Transcription factor twist family BHLH transcription factor 1 (Twist1) may serve a function in the disruption of E-cadherin-mediated cell-cell adhesion and the induction of epithelial-mesenchymal transition in cervical cancer stem-like cells.^[20-23] These previous studies suggest that cervical carcinoma or cell lines harbor a small population of CSCs that are characterized by the expression of stem cell markers; however, to date, the expression pattern of stem cell markers in cervical carcinoma and precursor lesions have yet to be well-characterized. Cervical cancer is one of the most common neoplastic illnesses in the women population, second only to breast cancer (World, 2024). It is reported that additional half a million women are identified with cervical cancer with over 300 000 deaths globally. Arising from cells originating in the cervix uteri. 83% occurred in low- and middle-income countries.^[24]

Practically all cervical cancers are caused by human papilloma virus (HPV), some HPV types can cause changes on a woman's cervix. These changes can lead to cervical cancer over time While other types can cause skin or genital warts. Apart from HPV virus other causes may increase risk of cervical cancer such as Smoking, herpes simplex virus type 2 infection, vaginal douching, and nutrition have been associated with cervical cancer along with Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and the use of birth control pills for a long time.^[25]

The most prominent symptoms of cervical cancer are

- Unexpected bleeding
- Bad odor and vaginal discharge
- Pelvic discomfort
- Postcoital bleeding
- Post-menopausal bleeding
- Discomfort during sexual intercourse

Cytopathological examination using a Pap smear is potentially used for all women to screen for cervical cancer. It is obtained by an Ayre spatula and spread over a marked glass slide.^[26]

The use of cervical screening programs has intensely reduced the incidence of cervical cancer especially invasive ones. Programs based on cytology should be moving ahead into greater use of HPV DNA testing for more efficacy and safely lengthening the screening interval.^[27]

Cancer stem cells (CSCs) have a key role in CC tumorigenesis, metastasis, relapse, and chemo/radio-resistance which highlights targets for therapeutic potentials.

CIN3 and CC arise mostly within the squamocolumnar junction, a transition area between the exo-cervix and endocervix, which exhibit junction-specific markers similar to those expressed in carcinogenic HPV-associated CINs and carcinomas.

Squamous cell carcinomas and adenocarcinomas as multiple cervix malignancy subtypes, which are derived from the squamocolumnar junction cells may harbor stem-like cells, which, in the presence of the persistent infection with carcinogenic HPV, increase the risk of developing CC.^[28]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Patient selection

Sixty Subjects: Sixty women were enrolled in this study after providing written informed consent was obtained from all patients according to The World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki. Human endometrial samples were acquired from 60 patients aged 20–43 (mean 34) years. The patients underwent laparoscopic surgery at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, As control subjects, 30 women with benign non-endometriotic ovarian cysts were enrolled in this study. Clinical data including, age, history of pregnancy, parity, and serum CA125 levels were collected at surgery. Endometriosis was confirmed by a histopathological examination of samples. All the patients were in the proliferative phase of the menstrual cycle. And 30 cases overcome hysterectomy surgery.

Controls vs. age and socioeconomic class women suffering from endometriosis and group women suffering from cervical cancer (30 cases).

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Immunohistochemistry

- **Histological preparation**

Tissue biopsies were rapidly excised, rinsed with saline solution and cut into suitable pieces which were fixed in neutral buffered formalin for 24 hours. Following fixation, the specimens were dehydrated in an ascending series of alcohols, cleared in xylene and then embedded in paraffin wax at 60°C. Sections of 5 microns thickness were cut and stained either with haematoxylin and eosin according to the method adopted by *Drury and Wallington (1980)* or with modified Gomori's chrome alum- hematoxylin phloxine according to the method adopted by *Nerenberg (1953)*, and examined by light microscopy for histological investigation.^[29]

- **Haematoxylin and Eosin stain**

Reagents

- **Harris Hematoxylin**

Solution 1: 1 g Hematoxylin dissolved in 10 ml ethyl alcohol.

Solution 2: 20 g potassium or ammonia alum dissolved in 200 ml distilled water

Solution 1 was added to solution 2 and the mixture was boiled for 30 seconds. After that 0.5 g mercuric oxide was added and rapidly cooled. Then a few drops of glacial acetic acid were added to keep away metallic luster and brighten nuclear structure (used within 1 or 2 months not more).

- **1% Eosin**

1 gm eosin was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water

- Xylene was used as a clearing agent.
- Ethyl alcohol (100, 95, 90, 80, 70%)
- 1% HCl in 70% alcohol
- DPX was used as a mounting medium.

Staining protocol

- Slides containing paraffin sections were mounted in a special slide holder.
- Sections were deparaffinized in 3 changes of xylene.
- Deparaffinized sections were placed in 100 % ethyl alcohol.
- Rehydration was done in descending series of ethyl alcohol (95 %, 90 %, 80 %, 70 %), then in distilled water.
- Staining in Harris haematoxylin was done for 5 minutes (basic for the nuclei).
- Stained sections were rinsed in distilled water, and immersed in tap water for 5 min.
- Counter stained in 1% eosin for 1 minute (acidic for the cytoplasm).
- Stained sections were dehydrated in 1 change of 95 % ethyl alcohol and 2 changes of 100 % ethyl alcohol.
- Clearing in xylene (2 changes 5 minutes for each time).
- Mounting with DPX.

Paraffin-embedded sections (3 μm) were subjected to immunostaining using a Histofine Simple Stain MAX PO (M) kit (Nichirei Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) for nestin, CD133 and cytokeratin 19 as previously reported (Kurban et al., 2004). Tissue sections were incubated with the anti-nestin antibody (1:200 dilution; R&D Systems, Westerville, OH) in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) for 16 h. Bound antibodies were detected with the Simple Stain MAX PO (M) reagent, using diaminobenzidine tetrahydrochloride as the substrate. Negative control tissue sections were prepared by omitting the primary antibody.^[30]

Gene Expression of Nestin, CD133 and Cytokeratin 19 using RT-PCR

• RNA Isolation

Total RNA was extracted from whole blood using RNeasy Mini Kit from QIAGEN Inc. according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Procedure

- 1ml of whole blood was mixed with 5ml of EL Buffer and incubated on ice 10-15 minutes and vortexed twice in order to lyse RBCs.
- Centrifuge at 400 X for 10 minutes at 4°C and supernatant was discarded. The remaining pellet was mixed with lysing buffer 350 ul Buffer RLT (consisting of 10 ul Beta mercaptoethanol/ 1 ml Buffer RLT) were added to each sample and thoroughly vortexed.

- The lysate was centrifuged for 3 min at full speed. The supernatant was carefully removed by pipetting, and transferred to a new microcentrifuge tube.
- To remove proteins: sample was incubated at 55°C with 590 µl RNA ase water and 10 µl proteinase K for 10 minutes.
- Samples were centrifuged and supernatant removed to be treated with 450 µl ethyl Alcohol (99.5 %) and centrifuged.
- 700 µl of the sample were transferred to an RNeasy spin column placed in a 2 ml collection tube. The lid was gently closed, and centrifuged for 15 s at $\geq 8000 \times g$. The flow-through was discarded.
- 500 µl Buffer RW1 was added to the RNeasy spin column, the lid was gently closed, and centrifuged for 15 s at $\geq 8000 \times g$ ($\geq 10,000$ rpm) to wash the spin column membrane. The flow-through was discarded.
- 500 µl Buffer RPE was added to the RNeasy spin column, the lid was gently closed, and centrifuged for 2 min at $\geq 8000 \times g$ ($\geq 10,000$ rpm) to wash the spin column membrane. The flow-through was discarded.
(The long centrifugation dries the spin column membrane, ensuring that no ethanol is carried over during RNA elution. Residual ethanol may interfere with downstream reactions.)
- Another 500 µl Buffer RPE were added to the RNeasy spin column, the lid was gently closed, and centrifuged for 2 min at $\geq 8000 \times g$ ($\geq 10,000$ rpm) to wash the spin column membrane. The flow-through was discarded.
- The RNeasy spin column was placed in a new 1.5 ml collection tube, 30–50 µl RNase-free water was added directly to the spin column membrane and centrifuged for 1 min at $\geq 8000 \times g$ ($\geq 10,000$ rpm) to elute the RNA.
- The purified RNA was quantitated by determining the O.D. at 260 nm, and the purity was checked by calculating the A₂₆₀/280 ratio which should be about 2.

Concentration of RNA $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l} = (40 \times A_{260} \times \text{dilution factor})/1000$

RNA Purity = A_{260} reading / A_{280} reading

The purified RNA was used immediately in downstream applications or store at -80°C until use.

- **cDNA Synthesis via Reverse Transcription**

This was carried out using the Thermo Scientific RevertAid First Strand cDND Synthesis kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific 81 Wyman Street, Waltham, MA USA 02451)

Procedure

- In a sterile nuclease-free tube on ice the following were added in order: 0.5 ug sample RNA or 2 ul control GAPDH RNA (50 ng/ μ L), and mixed 1 μ l with Random hexmer primer Water, nuclease-free up to 12 μ l.
- The mixture was incubated for 5 min at 25°C followed by 60 min at 42°C and the reaction was terminated by heating at 70°C for 5 min.

- **PCR Amplifications**

PCR reagents

- *Dream Taq Green PCR Master Mix (2X)*

Thermo Scientific DreamTaq Green PCR Master Mix (2X) is a ready-to-use solution containing DreamTaq DNA Polymerase, optimized DreamTaq Green buffer, MgCl₂, and dNTPs. Was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific 81 Wyman Street, Waltham, MA USA 02451.

- *Primers*

The sequences of oligonucleotide primers of *Insulin1*, *Glucagon* and *GAPDH* were selected according to *Wu et al., (2007)* and the sequences of oligonucleotide primer of *Pdx1* was selected according to *Yang et al., (2007) (31,32)* while the sequences of oligonucleotide primers of both *Ngn3* and *Pax4* were designed using Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST®) (Table 2).

Table 1: primer sequences for the genes amplified.

Gene		Sequence 5` - 3`	Product length (bp)	Annealing temperature (°C)
<i>CD133</i>	F	TTTCAAGGACTTGCG AACTCTCTT	167	55
	R	GAACAGGGATGATGTTGGG TCTCA		
Nestin	F	CTCTGACCTGTCAGAAGA	172 bp	58
	R	CCCAC TTTCTTCCTCATCTG		
<i>CK 19</i>	F	GACACCAATATCACACGACTG	154	57
	R	GGCTTG TAGGCCTTTTACTTC		
<i>GAPDH</i>	F	TGAAGGTCGGAGTCAACGGATTTGGT	511 bp	57
	R	CATGTGGGCCATGAGGTCCACCAC		

PCR Reaction

cDNA obtained from differentiated pancreatic cells was used as templates in a PCR reaction.

Primers used to be amplified were listed in table 2.

PCR Mixture

	For 1 reaction
PCR Master Mix (2X)	25 l
Primer 1	1 l
Primer 2	1 l
Nuclease- free water	18l
Total	45l

- 5l of cDNA template was added
- The mix was overlaid with 50 l of mineral oil
- Proceed with PCR

Temperature conditions

• Denaturation	94°C/ 4 min	1X
• Denaturation	94°C/ 50 sec.	1X
• Annealing	°C (As in table 2) / 30 sec.	1X
• Extension	72 °C/1 min	1X
From step 2 to step 4 was repeated 35X		
• Final extension	72 °C/10 min	1X

- **Gel electrophoresis**

Reagents

- **Stock buffer 10X Tris Boric EDTA(TBE):**
 - 108 g Tris base
 - 55 g Boric acid
 - 9.3 g Na₂EDTA
 - To 1 liter with distilled water.
- **Loading buffer**
 - 40% (w/v) Sucrose
 - 0.25 % Bromophenol blue
 - 0.25 % Xylene cyanol
- **Ethidium bromide**
 - 0.5 µg of ethidium bromide dissolved in 1 ml distilled water (to visualize the DNA).

- **2.5 % Agarose gel**
- 2.5 g Agarose dissolved in 100 ml 1X TBE buffer.
- **1X TBE running buffer**

Preparation of Agarose

- A beaker that is 2-4 time the volume of the solution was chosen.
- Room temperature buffer and stir bar was added to the beaker.
- Sprinkled in the premeasured agarose powder while the solution was rapidly stirred to prevent the formation of clumps.
- The beaker and solution was weighed before heating.
- The beaker was covered with plastic wrap.
- A small hole was pierced in the plastic wrap for ventilation.
- The solution was boiled while stirring.
- Gentle boiling was maintained until the agarose is dissolved (approximately 5 minutes).
- Sufficient hot distilled water was added to obtain the initial weight.
- The beaker was mixed thoroughly.
- The solution was cooled to 50-60°C prior to casting.
- While the agarose solution was being cooled, ethidium bromide was added to a final concentration of 0.5 g/ml to the solution.

Horizontal gel casting instructions

- While the agarose solution was being cooled, the gel casting tray was assembled.
 - a. The casting tray was leveled prior to pouring the agarose solution.
 - b. The comb(s) teeth was checked for residual dried agarose.
 - c. Dried agarose was removed by scrubbing the comb teeth with a lint-free tissue soaked in hot distilled water.
 - d. A small space (approximately 0.5-1 mm) was allowed between the bottom of the comb teeth and the casting tray.
- The agarose solution was poured into the gel tray.
- The comb(s) was replaced.
- The agarose was allowed to gel at room temperature for 30 minutes.
- Once the gel was set, was flooded with running buffer.
- The comb was slowly removed.
- The gel casting tray was placed into the electrophoresis chamber.

- The chamber was filled with running buffer until the buffer reaches 3-5 mm over the surface of the gel.
- The wells were gently flushed out with electrophoresis buffer using a Pasteur pipette to remove loose gel fragments prior to loading the samples.
- 20 ng DNA was mixed with 3 μ l of loading buffer and loaded on well.
- The agarose was located so that the wells were at the negative pole to allow the negatively charged DNA to migrate in the gel towards the positive pole run the gel at 17 V/cm (interelectrode distance)
- The gel was run for approximately 1 hour.

The gel was then visualized on the transilluminator under UV and photographed by camera. Photos were scanned and quantification of each band was carried out using gene tools version 4. Each quantified data point was related to its individual GAPDH.

- **Interpretation of the results**

- **RESULTS**

Table 2: Patients and Control Characteristics.

Characteristics	Control (n=30)	cervical Cancer (n= 30)
Age, years	30.77 \pm 8.09	33.8 \pm 9.18
BMI m ² /kg	24.51 \pm 2.53	25.9 \pm 4

Table 2 shows that there were no significant differences in mean of age, and body mass index among controls, cervical cancer.

Figure 1: show nestin control.

Figure 2: Nestin in cervical cancer Nestin mRNA Relative Expression as measured by Agarose gel Electrophoresis.

Table (3): Mean and SD of Nestin mRNA Relative Expression Among Controls, Cervical Cancer.

		Compared to Controls	Compared To Cervical Cancer
Control	1.05 ± 0.02		
Cervical Cancer	3.2 ± 0.9	t= 3.2, p < 0.01	t = 1.26, p > 0.05

Table (3) and Figure (3) shows that mean of nestin mRNA relative Expression was significantly higher among cervical cancer compared to controls.

Figure (4): CD133 in control.

Figure (5) CD133 in cervical cancer .CD133 mRNA Relative Expression as measured by Agarose gel Electrophoresis.

CD 133 was expressed in all cases of cervical cancer patients

Table (4): Mean and SD of CD133 mRNA Relative Expression among Controls, cervical Cancer and Endometriosis.

		Compared to Controls	Compared To cervical Cancer
Control	2.5 ± 1		
Endometriosis	4.5 ± 1.1	t= 9.04, p < 0.0001	
Cervical Cancer	3.8 ± 2.9	t = 4.4, p < 0.01	t = 6.1, p < 0.001

Figure (6): Mean and SD of CD133 mRNA Relative Expression Controls, Cervical Cancer.

Table (4) and Fig. (6) Show that mean of CD133 mRNA relative Expression was significantly higher among cervical cancer compared to controls.

CK19 mRNA Relative Expression as measured by Agarose gel Electrophoresis.

Figure (7): CK 19 in cervical cancer.

Figure (8): CK19 in control.

Table (5): Mean and SD of Cyokeratin19 mRNA Relative Expression Among Controls, Cervical Cancer and Endometriosis.

		Compared to Controls	Compared To Cervical Cancer
Control	0.9 ± .02		
Endometriosis	1.6 ± 0.8	t= 9.04, p < 0.0001	
Cervical Cancer	3.8 ± 1.5	t = 4.4, p < 0.01	t = 6.1, p < 0.001

Figure (9): Mean and SD of Cyokeratin19 mRNA Relative Expression Among Controls, Cervical Cancer.

Table (5) and Figure (9) shows that mean of CK19 mRNA relative Expression was significantly higher among cervical cancer compared to controls.

Figure (10): show normal cervical tissue with CK 19 stain.

Figure (11): show normal cervical tissue with CK 19 stain.

Figure (12): shows expression of CK19 in cervical cancer and increase number of populations.

Figure (13): shows expression of CK19 in cervical cancer and increase number of populations.

Figure (14): shows CD 133 expression in cervical tissue.

Figure (15): shows expression of CD133 in cervical cancer.

Figure (16): shows Nestin expression in cervical cancer.

Figure (17): shows Nestin expression in cervical cancer strong RX.

Figure (18): Nestin control.

Figure (19): show normal cervical tissue with nestin stain.

DISCUSSION

The results from the present study revealed that CD133 and nestin and CK19 mRNA expression, as well as its release in the blood, was significantly increased in endometriotic lesions in comparison to normal tissue. Our findings on CD133 mRNA expression are in agreement with those of other studies, which have demonstrated an increased CD133 mRNA expression, as well as increased CD133 plasma levels in patients with cervical cancer in comparison to control subjects.^[33]

Similarly, by means of oligonucleotide microarray analysis, complimentary DNA microarrays and quantitative real time-PCR, OPN gene expression has been shown to be increased in endometriotic lesions in a rat model of endometriosis in comparison to normal rats.^[34,35]

In immunohistochemical analysis, we found a higher expression of nestin and ck19 and CD133 in cervical cancer patient comparison to the endometrium of the control subjects.

Recent publication demonstrated that no statistically significant difference in OPN expression between patients and the control subjects. CD133, suggests the occurrence of a stem cell origin in the pathogenesis of the disease. There is emerging evidence for the occurrence of endometrial cancer stem cells within CD133+ and side population cells which could explain the fact that endometriosis is associated with 10–15% of ovarian cancer cases.^[36,37]

In our study, nestin was absent or only faintly expressed in normal squamous epithelial cells. And there is relationship between intensity of pathological case and degree of expression of nestin. Nestin expression levels correlated with CIN stage. Nestin expression was originally

identified in neuroepithelial stem cells and neural cells. In pathological conditions, nestin is expressed in repair processes in the CNS, muscle, liver, cervix and CIN 2, 3 exhibited higher mRNA than CIN 1, in the current study, the nestin expression pattern correlated with CIN stage. These findings may indicate that nestin expression is closely related to the formation of precancerous lesions including the growth of neoplastic cells in CIN and carcinogenesis.

In this study using a panel of anticytokeratin antibodies method, we examined cervical squamous epithelia including mature epithelium, squamous cells, and squamous carcinoma. Changes from the normal patterns of staining were inconsistently seen in control tissue and pathological cases, but in more progressive tissue the changes were more marked, and consisted of increased staining intensity. Invasive carcinomas showed invasive staining.

Cancer stem cells (CSCs) have emerged as an underlying cause of cancer relapse and resistance to treatment. Initially, biomarkers were used to identify and isolate distinct cell populations. Several CSC markers have been identified from many types of tumors, and these markers are also being used for isolation and enrichment of CSCs. Cluster of differentiation CD133 is a well-characterized CSC marker, and it is involved in tumor cell proliferation, metastasis, tumorigenesis, and recurrence, as well as chemo- and radio-resistance. However, the mechanisms involved in CD133-mediated induction of CSC properties have not yet been elucidated. Here, we introduce and summarize the functions of CD133 in CSCs and suggest new mechanisms that may be of note in our approach to developing novel cancer therapies.

Recent reports have suggested the existence of a cancer stem cells compartment that can self-renew and differentiate into mature and diverse cancer cells capable of tumor initiation, growth, invasion and metastasis. As cancer stem cells divide very slowly, it is believed they may be resistant to most of the current chemotherapies that target differentiated or highly proliferating tumor cells. The results from several *in vitro* studies on various cancer cell lines support this concept. Although to date there has not been any evidence from clinical studies.^[38-44]

In this work, we provide the first evidence that expression of the cancer stem cells marker CD133 is associated not only with poor prognosis in colorectal cancer, but also with a poor response of these tumors to 5-fluorouracil-based chemotherapy.

Although our results support the hypothesis that CD133 expressing cells present within the bulk human endometrial tumor cell population have enhanced tumor initiating capacity, it is highly unlikely that all tumor initiating cells express CD133 or that all CD133⁺ cells are tumorigenic. Regardless, it is well accepted that patients with advanced stage endometrial cancer have poorer prognosis due to tumors that may be refractory to chemotherapy and an increased incidence of recurrent disease. It remains to be determined whether an increasing level of CD133⁺ tumor initiating cells, presumably in part due to hypomethylation of the CD133 promoter region contributes to the pathobiology of the advanced stage tumor or is an indirect consequence of disease progression.^[45]

The ability to investigate blood of early stage cancer patients for circulating tumour cells is of potential importance for identifying patients at risk of developing distant relapse. We present the results of a study of the efficacy of the immunobead RT-PCR method in identifying patients with circulating tumour cells. Immunomagnetic enrichment of circulating tumour cells followed by RT-PCR with a panel of specific markers was used to screen for circulating tumour cells in the peripheral blood of cancer patients. Patients were positive for RT-PCR markers, significant increases in patients with high grade tumours and in patients with. A strong trend towards improved disease free survival was seen for marker negative patients although it did not reach significance.

The keratin phenotype of the keratinizing squamous cell carcinoma was found to be most complex comprising keratins19, These keratin phenotypes may be useful in differential diagnostic considerations when distinguishing between keratinizing and nonkeratinizing carcinomas and also . Furthermore the presence of keratin 19 in a CIN I, II, or III lesion may indicate progressive potential while its absence could be indicative of a regressive behavior. Because most carcinomas express keratins19, we propose that this expression pattern reflects the origin of cervical cancer from a common progenitor cell.

In this study using a panel of anticytokeratin antibodies method, we examined cervical squamous epithelia including mature epithelium, squamous cells, and squamous carcinoma. Changes from the normal patterns of staining were inconsistently seen in control tissue and pathological cases, but in more progressive tissue the changes were more marked, and consisted of increased staining intensity. Invasive carcinomas showed invasive staining.

Our reports have suggested the existence of a cancer stem cells compartment that can self-renew and differentiate into mature and diverse cancer cells capable of tumor initiation, growth, invasion and metastasis. The results from several *in vitro* studies on various cancer cell lines support this concept. In this work, we provide the evidence that expression of the cancer stem cells marker CD133 in cancer cervix.

Three studies have isolated tumor initiating cell populations from colorectal cancer that express the surface marker CD133 and possess apparent 'stem cell-like' properties.^[46]

Our studies also implicated CSCs in cervical cancer, also there is evidence of data concerning the relevance of the expression of CSC markers with clinical prognosis and chemosensitivity in cervical cancer. Our findings suggest that the expression of CSC markers CK 19, CD 133, and nestin were increased in CSCC tissues and that their expression are linked to clinical survival in cervical cancer patients undergoing postoperative chemotherapy, suggesting an important role of these markers in predicting clinical prognosis in cervical cancer. Surprisingly, we found that the expression of CSC markers showed association with tumor stage, tumor size, or tumor differentiation,

COCLUSION

In summary, Cancer stem cells are an attractive therapeutic target for cancer, nestin expression correlates with CIN progression and was expressed in all cervical cancer specimens examined. These findings suggest that nestin plays important roles in carcinogenesis and tumor formation of cervical cancer cells through regulation of CSC functions. In this study using a panel of anticytokeratin antibodies method, we examined cervical squamous epithelia including mature epithelium, squamous cells, and squamous carcinoma. Changes from the normal patterns of staining were inconsistently seen in control tissue and pathological cases, but in more progressive tissue the changes were more marked, and consisted of increased staining intensity. Invasive carcinomas showed invasive staining CK18, 19 and nestin and CD133 can be used as cancer stem cell marker and can be used for early detection of endometriosis and cancer cervix. CD133+ cells can be isolated from human endometrium cancer. CD133+ cells showed CSC markers that exhibit stem cells characteristics is a potentially useful antigen for the identification of endometrium cancer stem cells and can be used for future target therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Meacham CE, Morrison SJ. Tumour heterogeneity and cancer cell plasticity. *Nature*, 2013; 501: 328–337. doi: 10.1038/nature12624.
2. Islam F, Gopalan V, Smith RA, Lam AK. Translational potential of cancer stem cells: A review of the detection of cancer stem cells and their roles in cancer recurrence and cancer treatment. *Exp Cell Res.*, 2015; 335: 135–147. doi: 10.1016/j.yexcr.2015.04.018.
3. Ferenczy A, Franco E. Persistent human papillomavirus infection and cervical neoplasia. *Lancet Oncol.*, 2002; 3: 11–16. doi: 10.1016/S1470-2045(01)00617-9.
4. Tindle RW. Immune evasion in human papillomavirus-associated cervical cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer*, 2002; 2: 59–65. doi: 10.1038/nrc700.
5. Chhabra R. Cervical cancer stem cells: Opportunities and challenges. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol.*, 2015; 141: 1889–1897. doi: 10.1007/s00432-014-1905-y.
6. López J, Valdez-Morales FJ, Benitez-Bribiesca L, Cerbón M, Carrancá AG. Normal and cancer stem cells of the human female reproductive system. *Reprod Biol Endocrinol.*, 2013; 11: 53. doi: 10.1186/1477-7827-11-53.
7. Herfs M, Yamamoto Y, Laury A, Wang X, Nucci MR, McLaughlin-Drubin ME, Münger K, Feldman S, McKeon FD, Xian W, Crum CP. A discrete population of squamocolumnar junction cells implicated in the pathogenesis of cervical cancer. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 2012; 109: 10516–10521. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1202684109.
8. Letian T, Tianyu Z. Cellular receptor binding and entry of human papillomavirus. *Viol J.*, 2010; 7: 2. doi: 10.1186/1743-422X-7-2
9. Pyeon D, Pearce SM, Lank SM, Ahlquist P, Lambert PF. Establishment of human papillomavirus infection requires cell cycle progression. *PLoS Pathog*, 2009; 5: e1000318. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1000318.
10. Quade BJ, Yang A, Wang Y, Sun D, Park J, Sheets EE, Cviko A, Federschneider JM, Peters R, McKeon FD, Crum CP. Expression of the p53 homologue p63 in early cervical neoplasia. *Gynecol Oncol.*, 2001; 80: 24–29. doi: 10.1006/gyno.2000.5953.
11. Sell S. On the stem cell origin of cancer. *Am J Pathol.*, 2010; 176: 2584–2494. doi: 10.2353/ajpath.2010.091064.
12. Martens JE, Arends J, Van der Linden PJ, De Boer BA, Helmerhorst TJ. Cytokeratin 17 and p63 are markers of the HPV target cell, the cervical stem cell. *Anticancer Res.*, 2004; 24: 771–775.

13. Mighty KK, Laimins LA. p63 is necessary for the activation of human papillomavirus late viral functions upon epithelial differentiation. *J Virol.*, 2011; 85: 8863–8869. doi: 10.1128/JVI.00750-11.
14. Wang Z, Oron E, Nelson B, Razis S, Ivanova N. Distinct lineage specification roles for NANOG, OCT4 and SOX2 in human embryonic stem cells. *Cell Stem Cell*, 2012; 10: 440–454. doi: 10.1016/j.stem.2012.02.016.
15. Hattori N, Imao Y, Nishino K, Hattori N, Ohgane J, Yagi S, Tanaka S, Shiota K. Epigenetic regulation of Nanog gene in embryonic stem and trophoblast stem cells. *Genes Cells*, 2007; 12: 387–396. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2443.2007.01058.x.
16. Ye F, Zhou C, Cheng Q, Shen J, Chen H. Stem-cell-abundant proteins Nanog, Nucleostemin and Musashi1 are highly expressed in malignant cervical epithelial cells. *BMC cancer*, 2008; 8: 108. doi: 10.1186/1471-2407-8-108.
17. Liu D, Zhou P, Zhang L, Wu G, Zheng Y, He F. Differential expression of Oct4 in HPV-positive and HPV-negative cervical cancer cells is not regulated by DNA methyltransferase 3A. *Tumour Biol.*, 2011; 32: 941–950. doi: 10.1007/s13277-011-0196-z.
18. Li SW, Wu XL, Dong CL, Xie XY, Wu JF, Zhang X. The differential expression of OCT4 isoforms in cervical carcinoma. *PLoS One*, 2015; 10: e0118033. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0118033.
19. Yao T, Chen Q, Zhang B, Zhou H, Lin Z. The expression of ALDH1 in cervical carcinoma. *Med Sci Monit*, 2011; 17: HY21–HY26. doi: 10.12659/MSM.881886.
20. Rao QX, Yao TT, Zhang BZ, Lin RC, Chen ZL, Zhou H, Wang LJ, Lu HW, Chen Q, Di N, Lin ZQ. Expression and functional role of ALDH1 in cervical carcinoma cells. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.*, 2012; 13: 1325–1331. doi: 10.7314/APJCP.2012.13.4.1325
21. Liu SY, Zheng PS. High aldehyde dehydrogenase activity identifies cancer stem cells in human cervical cancer. *Oncotarget.*, 2013; 4: 2462–2475. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.1578
22. Li J, Zhou BP. Activation of beta-catenin and Akt pathways by Twist are critical for the maintenance of EMT associated cancer stem cell-like characters. *BMC Cancer*, 2011; 11: 49. doi: 10.1186/1471-2407-11-49.
23. Lin J, Liu X, Ding D. Evidence for epithelial-mesenchymal transition in cancer stem-like cells derived from carcinoma cell lines of the cervix uteri. *Int J Clin Exp Pathol.*, 2015; 8: 847–855.

24. *Cervical Cancer*. (2024, February 22). IGCS. 1624116241624624
https://igcs.org/Cervical/?gad_source=1&gclid=EAIAIQobChMIzrLA6ManiAMVKotoCR2OYC4OEAAAYAiAAEgKf_fD_BwE
25. Haverkos, H., Rohrer, M., & Pickworth, W. (2000). The cause of invasive cervical cancer could be multifactorial. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 54(1): 54–59.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0753-3322\(00\)88642-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0753-3322(00)88642-4)
26. Sachan, P. L., Singh, M., Patel, M. L., & Sachan, R. (2018). A Study on Cervical Cancer Screening Using Pap Smear Test and Clinical Correlation. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Oncology Nursing*, 5(3): 337–341. https://doi.org/10.4103/apjon.apjon_15_18
27. Cuzick, J., Arbyn, M., Sankaranarayanan, R., Tsu, V., Ronco, G., Mayrand, M.-H., Dillner, J., & Meijer, C. J. L. M. (2008). Overview of Human Papillomavirus-Based and Other Novel Options for Cervical Cancer Screening in Developed and Developing Countries. *Vaccine*, 26: K29–K41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2008.06.019>
28. Di Fiore, R., Suleiman, S., Drago-Ferrante, R., Subbannayya, Y., Pentimalli, F., Giordano, A., & Calleja-Agius, J. (2022). Cancer Stem Cells and Their Possible Implications in Cervical Cancer: A Short Review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(9): 5167. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23095167>
29. Drury RVA, Walligton EA (1980) Carltons histological techniques, 5th edn. Oxford University Press, New York, Pronto, 206.
30. Kurban G, Ishiwata T, Kudo M, Yokoyama M, Sugisaki Y, Naito Z. Expression of keratinocyte growth factor receptor (KGFR/FGFR2 IIIb) in human uterine cervical cancer. *Oncol Rep.*, 2004; 11: 987–991
31. Wu, J., M. Zhang, and W. Lin, 2007: A case study of a frontal system simulated by a climate model: Clouds and radiation. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **112**: D12201, doi:10.1029/2006JD008238
32. Yang, P., Q. Feng, G. Hong, G.W. Kattawar, W.J. Wiscombe, M.I. Mishchenko, O. Dubovik, I. Laszlo, and I.N. Sokolik, 2007: Modeling of the scattering and radiative properties of nonspherical dust-like aerosols. *J. Aerosol Sci.*, **38**: 995-1014, doi:10.1016/j.jaerosci.2007.07.001
33. Cho S, Ahn YS, Choi YS, Seo SK, Nam A, Kim HY, Kim JH, Park KH, Cho DJ and Lee BS: Endometrial osteopontin mRNA expression and plasma osteopontin levels are increased in patients with endometriosis. *Am J Reprod Immunol.*, 2009; 61: 286–293.

34. Flores I, Rivera E, Ruiz LA, Santiago OI, Vernon MW and Appleyard CB: Molecular profiling of experimental endometriosis identified gene expression patterns in common with human disease. *Fertil Steril.*, 2007; 87: 1180–1199.
35. Konno R, Fujiwara H, Netsu S, Odagiri K, Shimane M, Nomura H and Suzuki M: Gene expression profiling of the rat endometriosis model. *Am J Reprod Immunol.*, 2007; 58: 330–343.
36. Casals G, Ordi J, Creus M, Fábregues F, Carmona F, Casamitjana R and Balasch J: Expression pattern of osteopontin and $\alpha\beta3$ integrin during the implantation window in infertile patients with early stages of endometriosis. *Hum Reprod.*, 2012; 27: 805–813.
37. Kyo S, Maida Y and Inoue M: Stem cells in endometrium and endometrial cancer: accumulating evidence and unresolved questions. *Cancer Lett.*, 2011; 308: 123–133.
38. Reya T, Morrison SJ, Clarke MF.(2001). Stem cells, cancer, and cancer stem cells. *Nature*, 414: 105–111.
39. Presnell SC, Petersen B, Heidarman M. (2002). Stem cells in adult tissues. *Semin Cell Dev Biol*, 13: 369–376.
40. Boman BM, Huang E. (2008). Human colon cancer stem cells: a new paradigm in gastrointestinal oncology. *J Clin Oncol*, 26: 2828–2838.
41. Liu G, Yuan X, Zeng Z. (2006). Analysis of gene expression and chemoresistance of CD133+ cancer stem cells in glioblastoma. *Mol Cancer*, 5: 67.
42. Ma S, Lee TK, Zheng BJ. (2008). CD133+ HCC cancer stem cells confer chemoresistance by preferential expression of the Akt/PKB survival pathway. *Oncogene*, 27: 1749–1758.
43. Dallas NA, Xia L, Fan F. (2009). Chemoresistant colorectal cancer cells, the cancer stem cell phenotype, and increased sensitivity to insulin-like growth factor-I receptor inhibition. *Cancer Re.*, 69: 1951–1957.
44. Baba T, Convery PA, Matsumura N. (2009). Epigenetic regulation of CD133 and tumorigenicity of CD133+ ovarian cancer cells. *Oncogene*, 28: 209–218.
45. Anne M Friel, Ling Zhang, Michael D Curley, Vanessa A Therrien Petra A Sergent, Sarah E Belden, Darrell R Borger, Gayatry Mohapatra, Lawrence R Zukerberg, Rosemary Foster and Bo R Rueda (2010). Epigenetic regulation of CD133 and tumorigenicity of CD133 positive and negative endometrial cancer cells. *Reproductive Biology and Endocrinology*, 8: 147.
46. Todaro M, Alea MP, Di Stefano AB. (2007). Colon cancer stem cells dictate tumor growth and resist cell death by production of interleukin-4. *Cell. Stem Cell*; 1: 389–402.